

PREDICTING OLD FAITHFUL: A VIRTUAL FIELD TRIP VIA LIVE- WEBCAM TO YELLOWSTONE NATIONAL PARK

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Abstract

One recurring criticism of college coursework by students is the absence of meaningful application of the concepts and skillsets being taught. Employers have also voiced concern about graduates having superficial understanding of their specialty area focus. Making the transition from college to profession upon graduation is often daunting for graduates. New K-12 teachers have expressed feeling underprepared when they land their first teaching job. One such area is technology use in the classroom. Many in-service teachers have had a class specifically pertaining to educational technology, but feel the content was more about how to *use* technology, rather than how to *teach* with it. Unfortunately teaching labs (methods courses for example) generally target math, reading, social studies, and science fundamentals with less focus on other areas ubiquitous in society (technology for example). Even in these core realms applied uses of the concepts for meaningful, real-life scenarios are sometimes overlooked. Teacher Education programs that teach site-based courses, at an Elementary or Secondary school for instance, is one real-world application response implemented by programs. Another place that warrants increased use for applied learning is national parks.

National parks represent the largest natural science learning “laboratory” accessible to anyone in the world (Arnold & Castek, 2021). Comprised of 428 uniquely significant park sites (e.g., national parks, recreation areas, monuments, historic sites), the U.S. parks alone encompass over 52 million acres combined, equivalent to Kansas, the fifteenth largest state. Globally there are over 6500 national parks. The parks are natural conduits for learning about geology, flora, fauna, climate change, hydrology, astronomy, archeology, the human connection to these biomes, and more. Many of us may not remember our first science class, but we often remember our first visit to a national park (Arnold & Castek, 2021). The national park “season” in the U.S. for the northern parks is most commonly May to October, whereas it is November to April for parks along the southern border. Given its unique geothermal landscape and abundance of wildlife, Yellowstone National Park has a winter season as well that runs from mid-December to mid-March. An in-person visit to Yellowstone puts visitors in the actual natural environment with the possibility to see, hear, smell, feel, touch, hold, and ultimately experience some unique piece of the natural world using all the senses. An in-person visit to these vast natural learning labs is not attainable for everyone, and especially challenging for a class of K-12 or post-secondary students. Many national parks have taken steps to reach students who are unable to visit parks.

Through partnerships with Canon USA and the non-profit foundation Yellowstone Forever, Yellowstone National Park was able to implement multiple live-streaming webcams, essentially bringing Yellowstone to the connected world. The most popular webcam in Yellowstone also provides the most immersive experience. It is the Old Faithful and the Upper Geyser Basin Live-stream Webcam. It is a high-definition webcam mounted atop the Old Faithful Inn, and controlled by trained volunteers who are able to pan and zoom-in on any geothermal or wildlife activity in a 1.6 km² region of the Upper Geyser Basin (UGB). The UGB has one-fourth of the world's active geysers, and has some of Yellowstone's most famous wildlife, including grizzly bears, bison, elk, and wolves. In addition to the embedded live-stream webcam, the webpage hosting it also has current eruption predictions for five geysers (including Old Faithful), a “how-to” for predicting Old Faithful (OF), and a great deal of curated informative media for deeper learning about the geothermal features. It is a comprehensive resource, not only for visitors planning a visit, but also for K-12 teachers and college instructors teaching natural-resource related content. This research looks at a

combination of the latter two. An instructor of an Educational Technology course at a large U.S. university, and a park ranger of Yellowstone National Park implemented a project whereby pre-service teachers in the course had to spend time engaging the curated OF/UGB geothermal content, learn how to predict Old Faithful and why it works, log multiple hours watching the OF/UGB live-stream webcam, and create a narrated, explanatory screencast using Screencast-O-Matic of an Old Faithful eruption. Students had to be visually present speaking in the screencast, explaining the prediction and eruption process, and any other observations of the UGB that stood out. Preliminary analysis of student experiences in this study indicated that meaningful, applied technology use with a quasi-interactive live-streaming webcam interface made the participants confident they would (and will be able to) implement a similar project in their own K-12 classrooms. This was a significant difference as compared to other out of context, non-applied projects that felt more like assignments than real-world activities for their classrooms.

Keywords: Science, Environmental Education, National Parks, Technology, Virtual Learning, Experiential Learning, Service Learning, National Park Service, Park Ranger, Live-Stream, Webcam, Remote Learning, Geysers, Old Faithful, Upper Geyser Basin, Yellowstone, Teaching, Applied Learning